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Factors Influencing Dropouts at Undergraduate Level Students in Mogadishu, Somalia

Author's Details:

Sahal Adawe Abdulle¹, Mahdi Mohamed Omar²

sahaladawe@gmail.com

Abstract

every year many students get admitted into universities. However in 2024, many students are still struggling to complete their studies, especially undergraduate students. The main purpose of the study was to conduct and investigate the Factors Influencing on Dropouts at Undergraduate Level. A Case Study in Mogadishu, Somalia. A combination of quantitative and qualitative method was used. A dropout survey was developed to examine the factors influenced students to dropout. 207 students who had dropped out were asked reasoned behind their decision the specific objectives were to determine the effect family, Institutional, economic and social factor. The findings of the study show that the most important factors influencing students 'dropouts are the financial challenges, family related problems and social issues going third place, while intuitional factor are having a negative relation on dropout. Some recommendations based on the study findings have also been included in this paper.

Keywords: Dropout, Economic factor, Institutional factor, Family factor.

INTRODUCTION

Dropout is a serious issue for all developed and the developing countries of the world. In developing countries, drop out is one of the multiple indicators of the quality of educational system that highlights the existence of serious failures in the processes of orientation, transition, adaptation and the student body's promotion. for this reason, in the frame of the European space of higher education, a lot of universities are taking into account in their strategic plans a primary objective: reducing the rate of the student's drop out (araque et al., 2009). Dropout is defined as the interruption of studies by students in higher education enrolled for any length of time, regardless of university change before its conclusion. (bonaldo & nobre, 2016). Adolescents that drop out of school are at risk of low economic status even in adulthood due to unemployment, low paying jobs, alcoholism, poor health, committing crime and are prone to community detachment, all of which are of public health concern (Nabugoomu, 2021). As we know financial issues are one of the major reasons that lead students to drop out, especially in developing countries where most of their universities are private. Furthermore, most families are poor and struggle with their basic lives rather than dealing with students' payment fees and material they need, which may lead to dropout. (Arce et al., 2015). Some family economic difficulties or the lack of financial help for studying force some students to simultaneously study and work which in some cases induces situations of incompatibility that cause drop out. Nowadays a big percentage of students come from broken homes and the divorce of the parents also contributes to financial hardship (Araque et al., 2009b) (Srairi, 2021) students find difficulty in continuing their studies. Regarding family resources, which are measured by the parents' occupational status, education, and income, several studies report that students from poor families (especially in case parents' income is below the poverty line) or whose parents did not graduate from university are at greater risk of dropping out from university than students from families without these risk factors. Family practices or parental support are also indicated as a predictor of university dropout. Students of parents who

have high educational aspirations of their children and who monitor their children's university progress are more likely achieved their studies in universities. As said According to (Srairi, 2021) Factors related to the organizational and structural characteristics of university are also important to understand with regard to reasons for dropping out. Recently, the study finds that the differences in dropout were largely attributable to institutional structural and resource differences. University factors may include university resources, the curriculum, university regulations, and teacher quality. Universities' resources are most frequently defined by the institutional size and teacher-student ratio. Smaller institutional size and lower student/staff ratio may have a positive effect on university achievement. Most studies find a positive relationship between these two indicators and dropout rates. (Alban & Mauricio, 2019b) Dropout negatively affects education institutions in the reduction of enrolment and the non-achievement of educational institutional objectives. Furthermore, dropout becomes a critical topic when university administrators do not possess the tools necessary to identify students who are at risk of leaving the education institution. In turn, potential corrective measures are reduced, which might have enabled student retention at higher education institutions. In the same way, the early prediction of student dropout has become a major challenge, as well as identifying the factors which contribute to this increasingly occurring phenomenon. possible reason that there are still high university dropout rates may be associated with the fact that most of the prediction models applied to solve this problem are difficult to interpret, A significant effort has been made to close the university dropout gap and thus reduce dropout rates. Nonetheless, this effort has been insufficient. Social factors (the need to work; combining studies with work); difficulties associated with a lack of prior knowledge of the university environment; and little transparency in courses. "Other factors linked to the difficulty in transitioning from high school to university include changes in learning styles, requirement levels, and level of student responsibility, making it difficult to identify weighting factors that influence dropout (Stage, 1989). The social consequences of leaving education institutions early have been identified repeatedly, when a students drop out of education and fails in his or her attempt to find a job both student and society suffer. The study of suggested that the dropout who has experienced feelings of failure in education is greeted by society that is overtly hostile to dropouts, thus reinforcing his/her feelings of worthless (P. Larsen, 1987). In Somalia calculating an accurate dropout rate is nearly impossible, since schools differ in their definitions of a dropout, their counting methods, and their methods of following a student who drops and reenters, or those who leave the district and reenter another one (Jama, 2015). Studied, that factors influencing female students' dropout rate in secondary schools in Mogadishu, Somalia. It can be seen that these above studied did not investigate factors influencing dropouts at undergraduate level in Jamhuriya University of science and technology: a case study of just, Mogadishu, Somalia therefore the problem this study addressed to investigate the factors in which drive family, institutional, social and economic.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The research aimed to help a wide range of people in the following ways:

The study's findings might be used to encourage government and community opinion leaders in the Benadir region and throughout Somalia to endorse a campaign for student education. Educational authorities in Mogadishu were use the data to develop retention strategies for male and female students at Jamhuriya University. The study's findings are likely to assist officials about how to prepare for male and female enrolment at Jamhuriya University. Based on the documented level of male and female dropouts by region, the findings may also aid policymakers in developing policies to mitigate the factors influencing dropouts at the undergraduate level at Jamhuriya University of Science and Technology.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

According to (The State of Higher Education in Somalia: Privatization, Rapid Growth, and the Need for Regulation, 2013) there was a significant growth of the higher education sector between 2004 and 2012. Their report indicates that of 44 institutions they surveyed, 34 were established during this period. According to them, over 50,000 students are enrolled at HEIs across the country at the time. Most of these students are enrolled at universities in South-Central 49%, with the rest in Somaliland, and Puntland.

This is very encouraging since the country's central government and its institutions barely recovered from the collapse in 1991, with a little revival we have seen lately most inspired by civil society through privately owned higher education institutions offering a wide range of courses.

The majority of students are enrolled in information technology (IT), business administration and social science courses.

However, enormous numbers of students withdraw from higher education every year without completing the academic programs they were enrolled in due to limited financial resources, a shortage of learning materials, and insufficient basic infrastructure ranking high among the challenges facing HEIs.

There are a number of research work developed across Asia and elsewhere to determine the relationship between these factors and student dropout rates and also, tried to prove how and to what extent these factors affect students withdrawing from their programs prior to completing their studies.

However, the researchers couldn't find such work conducted in Somalia specifically in Mogadishu.

Therefore, the researchers sought to fill this gap by trying to investigate the factors influencing on dropouts at the undergraduate level in Jamhuriya University of Science and Technology (JUST) A Case Study in Mogadishu, Somalia.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To determine the effect family factor on student dropout in Jamhuriya University Mogadishu-Somalia.
2. To examine the effect social factor on student dropout in Jamhuriya University Mogadishu-Somalia.
3. To identify the effect institutional factor on student dropout in Jamhuriya University Mogadishu-Somalia.
4. To examine the effect economic factor on student dropout in Jamhuriya University Mogadishu-Somalia.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were guiding the study:

1. What are the effect family factors on student dropout in Jamhuriya University Mogadishu-Somalia?
2. What are the effect social factors on student dropout in Jamhuriya University Mogadishu-Somalia?
3. What are the effect institutional factors on student dropout in Jamhuriya University Mogadishu-Somalia?
4. What are the effect economic factors on student dropout in Jamhuriya University Mogadishu-Somalia?

METHODOLOGY

The case study was limed students' dropout at Jumhuriya University in 2019-2020 seasons. The study targeted a sample population of 207 dropout students who were selected a sample size of 136 students. 125 students participate the study and responded our questionnaire were 11 missed due lack available and not responded the study investigators communication. The study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional and regression research design with quantitative approach the study used a sample size and utilized both simple random sampling and stratified sampling methods in the selection of respondents. The study employed questionnaires as data collection tools the study used phone call to communicate with students, and arranged a group to ask questionnaire questions and write down their answers through questionnaire link that investigator sends WhatsApp by individuals and also in groups. In addition to better convenience in terms of time, stability, uniformity and consistency, this strategy was chosen by the researchers on the most suitable. The research achieved a response rate of 92% from the 125 respondents out of the 136 questionnaires were administered and distributed to the selected respondents of the study. The study was analyzed using the statistical package (SPSS) software and Microsoft excel.

Table of Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.879	20

Table of Validity

$$CVI = \frac{\text{number of items declared valid}}{\text{total number of items in the questionnaires}} = \frac{20}{20} = 1$$

Demographic variables	Frequency	Percentage%
Gender		
Male	98	78.4
Female	27	21.6
Total	125	100.0
Age		
20-25	117	93.6
26-30	7	5.6
31-35	1	0.8
Total	125	100.0
Marital Status		
Single	110	88.0
Married	15	12
Total	125	100%
Educational background		
Secondary	27	21.6
Diploma	18	14.4
Bachelor	80	64.0
Total	125	100.0
Work experience		
Less than one year	53	42.4
More than one year	58	46.4
Not worked	14	11.2
Total	125	100.0

Findings and Discussions

As shown in Table above, five factors were used to gather the demographic information relevant to the study. Gender was the first demographic variable in which the respondent was asked to clarify themselves as either males or females. Out of the 125 respondents 98 or 78.4% were males while 28 or 21.6% were females. This indicates a male domination of dropout students compared to females. But is understandable the study target population indicates domination of male compared to the female.

The second demographic variable asked the respondent age. Out of the 125 respondents 117(93.6%) were between 20 to 25 years old; 7(5.6%) were between 26 to 30 years old; and only 1(0.8%) were between 31 to 35 year old. The third one demographic variable asked the respondent marital status. Out of 125 respondents 110(88.0%) were single and 15(11.9%) were married.

The study also identified educational background of the respondents. Out of 125 respondents 27(21.6%) were secondary; 18 students or 14.4% have diploma and also 80 or 64.0% have bachelor. The fifth which is the last demographic variables asked to the respondents was worked experience. Out of 125 respondents 53 people or 42.4% work experience were less than one year, 58 or 46.4% work experience were more than one year while were 14 people or 11.2% not worked.

Table, Economic Factor

No.	Economic factor	SD	D	N	A	SA	Mean	St. Dev.
1	Poverty is the main reason for students to leave the college and education.	4	24	10	71	16	3.5680	1.04214
2	Part time job timing is also cause of students drop out.	8	30	22	53	12	3.2480	1.11916
3	Unemployment of educated people discourages you to leave the studies	8	32	8	64	13	3.3360	1.15664
4	Students drop out because lack of fee payment	6	24	12	66	17	3.5120	1.09703

The study sought to establish whether Poverty is the main reason for students to leave the college and education. The findings indicated that most of the respondents supported the view that the poverty has role students to dropout the education (Mean=3.5680, Std. Deviation=1.04214). The study also established whether Part time job timing is also cause of students drop out and the result shown in table above that majority of participants agree while (Mean=3.2480, Std. deviation=1.11916. Majority of the respondents also recounted as shown in 4.7 above that unemployment of educated people discourages students to leave the studies (Mean=3.3360, Std. deviation=1.15664). The studies investigated whether Students drop out because lack of fee payment. The findings in table 4.7 above indicate the issues surround lack fee payments due of financial reason has increase possibility of students to dropout, while majority of the respondents were in agree with the statement (Mean=3.5120, Std. deviation=1.09703).

Table, Institutional factor

No	Institutional factor	SD	D	N	A	SA	Mean	St. Dev.
1	Due to system of university constraints lead students drop out	4	33	22	52	14	3.3120	1.08074
2	Students drop out occur because of fear of failure in the exams at the graduate level.	10	41	11	55	8	3.0800	1.16120
3	Ineffective teaching-learning process contributes a lot to the dropout of the students.	3	33	24	56	9	3.2800	1.01282
4	Unsafety around university campus location cause students to dropout	10	46	15	40	14	3.0160	1.21140

Table 4.8 indicates the responses of participants about system of university constraints lead students drop out. The results revealed that university related the factors (Mean=3.3120, SD=1.16120) are reasonable factors of students' dropout. The findings revealed students fear of failure in the exams at the graduate level. (Mean=3.0800, SD=1.16120); Ineffective teaching-learning process (Mean=3.2800, SD=1.01282); unsafety around university campus location cause (Mean=3.0160, SD=1.21140) are the university related factors that causes students' dropout l. The main factors that cause dropout of students are shown in Figure.

Table, Family Factor

No	Family factor	SD	D	N	A	SA	Mean	St. Dev.
1	A large number of family members are the one cause of students drop out at graduate level.	7	32	16	62	8	3.2560	1.08438
2	Due to lack of parental interest, the students are dropped out at college level.	6	28	25	49	17	3.3440	1.11517

3	In order to support their families' students, leave the college education and get some jobs.	6	23	21	60	15	3.4400	1.07313
4	Families' faculty choice lead students drop out	4	28	19	55	19	3.4560	1.09621

In Table 4.9 indicates responses of participants about if a large number of family members are the one contributes of students drop out. The results revealed that family related the factors (Mean=3.2560, SD=1.08438) are one of the challenges of students' dropout. The findings revealed due to lack of parental interest, the students are dropped out at college level. (Mean=3.3440, SD=1.11517); In order to support their families' students, leave the college education and get some jobs (Mean=3.4400, SD=1.07313); Families' faculty choice (Mean=3.4560, SD=1.09621) are the family related factors that causes students' dropout. The main factors that cause dropout of students are shown in Figure.

Table, Social Factor

No	Social factor	SD	D	N	A	SA	Mean	St. Dev.
1	Mostly social ignores the importance of education which can lead students drop out	5	25	18	65	12	3.4320	1.04214
2	students drop out at college due to social discrimination	8	48	19	40	10	2.9680	1.13547
3	Students are expelled from college because of their involvement in groups.	4	35	25	51	10	3.2240	1.04214
4	Early marriage causes drop out of the students	5	44	14	46	16	3.19201	1.16879

As also shown in Table 4.9.1 indicates responses of participants about if social ignores the importance of education which can lead students drop out. The results revealed that social related the factors (Mean=3.4320, SD=1.04214) are one of the issues of students' dropout. The findings revealed students drop out at college due to social discrimination. (Mean=2.9680, SD=1.13547); Students are expelled from college because of their involvement in groups (Mean=3.4400, SD=1.07313); Early marriage causes drop out of the students (Mean=3.19201, SD=1.16879) as shown the table statistically social related factors that causes students' dropout.

MODEL SUMMARY TABLE

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.609 ^a	.371	.350	.53565
a. Predictors: (Constant), Social, Economic, institutional, Family				

The model summary results indicate that the coefficient of determination R was 0.609, Adjusted R-square was 0.35 and R square was .371 which indicates that 37% of the total variations are factors cause dropout, and the remaining 63% of the variations are causes by other factors.

ANOVA TABLE

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	20.272	4	5.068	17.663	.000 ^b
	Residual	34.431	120	.287		
	Total	54.703	124			
a. Dependent Variable: Dropout						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Social, Economic, institutional, Family						

In table findings above shown that the whole model of the study statistically is significant.

Since the p-value ($0.000 < 0.05$), this means that dropout has a negative, statistically moderate and significant and effects on the students in Jamahiriya university.

COEFFICIENT TABLE

Coefficients^a		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.413	.253		5.584	.000
	Economic	.342	.083	.398	4.123	.000
	Institutional	-.073	.087	-.085	-.838	.404
	Family	.157	.087	.186	1.796	.075
	Social	.154	.097	.175	1.595	.113
a. Dependent Variable: Dropout						

The study results suggested that when economic factor increases to 1%, dropout increases 34.2% which is statistically significant. There are several studies suggested that financial issues are one of the main issues contribute and increases dropout rates. (Moodley & Singh, 2015) maintains there is usually a combination of factors that leads to a student’s departure. In their study, they found that a lack of finance coupled with other factors was the most cited reason for students dropping out at the University of KwaZulu Natal. Many parents are unable to meet the financial demands of university which forces the need for financial aid. A major reason students discontinue their studies is because of a lack of finances. More specifically, students drop out because of the inability to fund tuition and books.

Furthermore, according the coefficient results assumed that institutional factor has positive relation with dropout. As result said if the rule of university restricts and increase 1% the dropout rate decreases 7.3% which the study result insists this variable insignificant while several researches mention of opposite, other studies suggest that institution participate dropout. According to (Alban & Mauricio, 2019b) Dropout negatively affects education institutions in the reduction of enrolment and the non-achievement of educational institutional objectives. Furthermore, dropout becomes a critical topic when university administrators do not possess the tools necessary to identify students who are at risk of leaving the education institution. In turn, potential corrective measures are reduced, which might have enabled student retention at higher education institutions.

Family factor increases 1% the dropout factor increases 15.7% although statistically is insignificant. Several studies show that family background (proxied by parents’ education or occupation) has a significant negative correlation with dropout behavior. For instance, (Moodley & Singh, 2015) find that the parents’ occupation plays a significant role in determining both educational attainment and voluntary dropout, providing evidence that students with unskilled parents are more at risk of failure. The cultural family background, proxied by the parents’ education level, does not seem to play a significant role and sometimes appears to be completely irrelevant in determining the time to degree completion. The education level and occupation of parents, altogether, do not only allow to determine the socio-economic conditions of students, but are also good proxies of family income, which has controversial effects on students’ academic outcomes. Raw data provide evidence that high school leavers coming from low-income families are generally less likely to attain a university degree than others.

Furthermore, a shown the table above when social factor increases 1%, dropout factor increases 15.4% although statistically is insignificant. According to (Moodley & Singh, 2015) withdrawal process depends on how students interact with the social and academic environment of the institution , researchers tend to place more emphasis on the influence of external environment, such as student’s occupation and support from their family, while the concept of social integration into an ODL institution’s cultural fabric, is given less weight.

Students enrolled in ODL are typically adults, attend part-time, and may be full-time jobholders who are also shouldering family responsibilities (McGivney, 2004). For such students, factors such as ‘lack of time,’ ‘poor guidance,’ ‘lack of feedback on assignments,’ ‘time management,’ ‘unrealistic expectations,’ and so on, all contribute to withdrawal. Other factors also reported include ‘lack of guidance and information prior to registering and enrollment,’ ‘lack of support from faculty,’ and difficulty ‘contacting faculty’ Personal Reasons, such as changes in status of employment or family circumstances, play an important role in determining withdrawals. Problems cited such as ‘lack of time’ are particularly acute, especially in cases where students are employed and/ or must shoulder domestic commitments. Such students, therefore, may not be in a position to balance their personal obligations and their educational pursuits, and are often left with little or no choice but to dropout.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study investigates that dropout rates seem to influence by student’s background. As we found that dropout of private universities is not due a single reason; there are various reasons behind which led students to dropout, one of the major reasons conducted by the study is low economic, financial struggle families and inability to afford educational costs. Family’s financial struggling take a huge role the dropout rate, also unemployment of educated people discourages students and participate to leave the college which is one of barriers related lack market job and financial instability faced students. There is other several studies assumed that financial problem is one of the main issues contribute and increases dropout rates as we mention chapter4. We also examine those social issues participates dropout rates, while family problems are one of the major causes contribute students to dropout. Based on study findings family contribute dropout rate, lack of parental awareness of student’s education, a large number of family members, in order to support their family and finding job demotivate students to complete the study which might lead to dropout. Furthermore, institutional factors and pressure of the study as one of the reasons. The study also suggested that the pressure of study and lack of communication between students and teachers demotivates students which cause poor results in exam which makes students to leave the college. If these factors are controlled, the dropout rate and the developing quality of education will be ensured. Therefore, the researchers recommended academic institutions should lower costs to all students and more specifically to those who cannot afford to study at fixed institutional prices also Parents should aware students learning process and their level based on their results and feedback of teachers. Furthermore, Permanent support through mentoring and tutoring services help keep students on track to graduate. This will guide students to continue their studies no matter what circumstances they face and parents should engage relationship with university administration to get relevant academic communications regarding their children.

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